

Re-definition of the NSL time scale: Implications for NDAC interfaces
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As suggested by Schuetz (note 'HIPPARCOS PSF Timing' dated 1988-12-12) and discussed by the HST on February 15, the time scale for the Nominal Scanning Law (NSL) will probably have to be defined in terms of spacecraft time rather than TAI (or UTC), as is presently the case. The change is motivated by the relatively large clock drift (up to a second per day), which would otherwise require very frequent updating of the clock correlations in order to avoid unacceptable discontinuities in the NSL.

From the viewpoint of the reduction consortia, the change only concerns the definition of the argument d in equation [1.6e] of the Hipparcos book (Volume III), which presently reads:

$$d = (t - T_{NSL}) / (1 \text{ mean solar day}) \quad (1)$$

with t denoting a continuous time scale such as TDT or TAI, and T_{NSL} being the origin epoch for the NSL, i.e. 1988 Jan 1, 12h00m00s UTC = 1988 Jan 1, 11h59m36s TAI = 1988 Jan 1, 11h59m03.816s TDT. The revised definition of d can be expressed in the form:

$$d = (t - T_{NSL}) / (1 \text{ mean solar day}) + \Delta d(t) \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta d(t)$ is the accumulated drift of the spacecraft clock from some initial time near the beginning of the mission up to time t . $\Delta d(t)$ is a continuous function which may be derived from datation information given in the telemetry headers.

In practice, the quantity d would be tied to the 'filing key' FK , which is a sequential numbering of the telemetry frames (nominally of 1/24 s duration) throughout the mission (or, at least, over significant parts of the mission). The filing key is an integer which refers to the beginning of each telemetry frame. By permitting a fractional part to FK we may extend this concept to become a continuous time scale locked to the spacecraft clock. Thus, the instant FK (in spacecraft time) falls within the telemetry frame specified by the filing key $INT(FK)$. With respect to this spacecraft time scale, the argument d to be used in the NSL can be written as:

$$d = d_0 + (FK - FK_0) / (86400 * 24) \quad (3)$$

where d_0 and FK_0 are constants to be specified by ESOC, and $86400 * 24$ is the nominal number of filing keys per day. It is assumed that d_0 and FK_0 will be chosen in such a way that (3) coincides with (1) at some time near the beginning of the mission.

This change in the definition of the NSL has one important consequence for the RGO/CUO and CUO/LO interfaces (and also the NDAC/TDAC interface for the attitude). The NDAC attitude angles (the 'heliotropic angles' ν , ξ , Ω) are defined relative to a frame which rotates with the 'nominal sun' according to a prescribed function of the argument d . If we accept to re-define d as described above, the information given in the present NDAC interfaces is not sufficient to interpret the heliotropic angles correctly. In order to resolve this problem, I can see two main possibilities (with numerous variants):

1. NDAC retains the present definition of d [equation (1)] for interfaces within NDAC and with TDAC, while (2) or (3) is used only for interpretation of the ESOC data.
2. In all interfaces giving the heliotropic angles, the relation between t (or NDAC frame number) and d (or the filing key) is somehow provided.

Solution 1 means that RGO must handle two different definitions of the heliotropic frame, which is most unattractive.

Perhaps the simplest variant of solution 2 would be to give, in the frame file and attitude file headers, the value of d at the mid-time of the first frame in the file. Since d is incremented by exactly $1/40500$ per observation frame it is then possible to derive it for any frame in the file e.g. as:

$$d = d_1 + (1/40500) * \text{NINT}(0.46875 * (\text{FMTIME} - \text{FMTBEG})) \quad (4)$$

where d_1 is the value of d at the mid-time of the first frame (FMTBEG), and FMTIME is the mid-time of the required frame. Note that the expression $\text{NINT}(0.46875 * (\text{FMTIME} - \text{FMTBEG}))$ simply gives the frame number relative to the first frame in the file. This expression can be used provided that all the frames in a file are nominally equidistant (in spacecraft time) and that the clock drift does not exceed half an observing frame (1.066 sec) during the interval covered by the file. The latter assumption may be a bit unsafe if the clock drift can really be as much as 1 sec per day. However, the frame and attitude file headers also give an absolute frame number for the first and last frame in the file (NFRBEG and NFREND, respectively). Thus, by using:

$$(\text{NFREND} - \text{NFRBEG}) / (\text{FMTEND} - \text{FMTBEG})$$

instead of the nominal frequency 0.46875 Hz in equation (4), one should always be on the safe side.

Other variants to solution 2, such as giving the filing key and on-board time of the first IDT sample (THFKEY and THOBTM, respectively, from the telemetry header) of the first observing frame in the file, would appear to be more complicated and less obvious. For instance, one would then also need to know d_0 and FK_0 .

My suggestion is that d_1 should be included in the header for the frame and attitude files. If it is expressed in seconds (through multiplication by 86400), it can be given as two 32-bit integers in the same way as the NDAC times (integral part and microseconds).

Note that we never need to know explicitly the quantity $\Delta d(t)$ appearing in equation (1), since all evaluations are made either in terms of d (the argument for the heliotropic frame and NSL) or t (the argument for astronomical ephemerides). Nevertheless, it may be interesting to evaluate $\Delta d(t)$ at a relatively high frequency as a means of monitoring the clock drift.